

at five sites in farmer fields in Punjab. NPK was applied at 120-13-24 kg/ha, based on the general recommendation. When fertilizer application was based on soil analysis, 25% more N and P and 25% less K were applied, except at site 5 (see table). Soils were deficient in DTPA extractable Zn and 10 kg Zn/ha was applied. Soils were medium-textured and alkaline

with low electrical conductivity, organic carbon, and available P and high available potash.

Data in the figure show the yield differences obtained by applying N, NP, NPK, and NPKZn. Application of NP increased yield 1.4 t/ha (30%) than applying N alone. Soils with P deficiency responded significantly to P application. Response to

applied K was small. When 50 kg ZnSO₄/ha + NPK were applied, yield increased 0.6 t/ha (12%) over yield with NPK alone.

Our research showed that applying only N fertilizer is not sufficient to maximize rice yield. A balanced application of nutrients, including Zn and S, based on soil analysis, results in optimum yield. □

Rice-Based Cropping Systems

Rice and air-breathing fish culture: effects of seasonal variations on the yields of grain, straw, and fish

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We studied the effects of seasonal variations on the yields of mixed cultures of air-breathing catfish Singhi (*Heteropnaustes fossilis*) and Magur (*Clarias batrachus*) and high yielding rices at ORP in pre-kharif (Mar-Jun), kharif (Jun-Nov), and boro (Nov-Apr) rice seasons. Rices Ratna, Pankaj, and Jaya were grown.

Experiments consisted of a control treatment of rice without fish and plots of rice with air-breathing fish. Plots were 35 × 10 m with a shallow 75- × 40-cm-perimeter canal, bounded by a dike. Equal numbers of Magur and Singhi fingerlings were stocked at 1 fish/m² 7 d after transplanting. Before stocking, they were

Effects of seasonal variations on the yield of grain, straw, and fish at ORP, Pandua, West Bengal, 1983-84.

Yield factor	Yield (t/ha)					
	Prekharif (Ratna)		Kharif (Pankaj)		Boro (Jaya)	
	Without fish	With fish	Without fish	With fish	Without fish	With fish
Grain	3.2	3.8	3.0	3.1	5.9	6.4
Straw	8.1	8.1	8.9	9.7	5.0	5.8
Fish	—	0.4	—	0.4	—	0.5

treated with a 100 ppm solution of formalin for 30 s. Each morning, fish were fed a low-cost 1:2 mixture of fishmeal and rice bran mixed with cowdung at 5% body weight. Fish were harvested with rice by draining the plots.

Soil was a clay loam with pH 6.5-7.0. Farmyard manure at 9 t/ha was applied to all plots during land preparation. The plots were plowed and 100 kg N/ha was applied: 1/2 at land preparation and 1/2 in equal splits 1 mo after transplanting and 1 wk before flowering. PK at 18-33 kg/ha was applied during tillage. Seedlings at 2/hill were transplanted at 15- × 15-cm spacing.

Standard cultivation methods were practiced and field water level was maintained at 8-10 cm. Plankton consisted mainly of *Spirogyra*, *Volvox*, *Ulothrix*, *Euglena*, *Pinularia*, *Monia*, *Cyclops*, *Keratella*, and *Brachionus*.

Combined rice and fish culture produced best in all seasons. Grain and fish yield were maximum in boro followed by pre-kharif and kharif (see table). Straw yield was maximum in kharif. Of the three varieties, Jaya performed best.

Stem borer population was highest in the control and least in rice-fish plots. □

Announcements

Meelu elected to ARRW Executive Committee

O. P. Meelu, senior research fellow, Multiple Cropping Department, IRRI, was elected Councilor (North Zone) to the Association of Rice Research

Workers of the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India, for 1984 and 1985. Meelu is actively engaged in research on fertilizer efficiency in rice and rice-based cropping sequences at Punjab Agricultural University. □

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